

A Study on Investors Attitude and Perception towards different Investment Avenues in Satara City

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Abstract:

In the present dynamic and rapidly evolving financial environment, investment decisions play a crucial role in ensuring financial security and achieving long-term wealth creation. Investors today are exposed to a wide range of investment avenues, making it essential to understand their attitudes and perceptions while selecting suitable options. This study focuses on analysing investor behaviour with special reference to Satara city, highlighting the importance of informed decision-making in a changing financial landscape.

The primary objectives of the study include examining the level of awareness among investors, identifying the factors influencing their investment decisions, assessing their risk appetite, analysing preferred investment avenues, and evaluating satisfaction with investment returns. The research adopts a descriptive research design and is based on primary data collected from 122 respondents through a structured questionnaire. Secondary data has also been used and sourced from books, journals, reports, and research articles to support the study.

The findings of the study reveal that a majority of respondents are young individuals, mainly students and salaried employees with moderate income levels. Traditional investment avenues such as fixed deposits, gold, and real estate are widely preferred due to their safety, stability, and lower perceived risk. Although investors generally exhibit a high level of awareness regarding various investment options, detailed financial knowledge remains moderate.

Further, factors such as safety of capital, expected return on investment, liquidity, tax benefits, and individual risk tolerance significantly influence investment decisions. Most investors display a moderate risk appetite and regularly monitor their investments. While satisfaction with individual investment avenues is largely positive, many respondents remain neutral regarding overall portfolio returns. The study highlights the need for improved financial literacy and awareness to enable investors to make informed and effective investment decisions.

Keywords: Investors Attitude, Investors Perception, Investment Avenues, Investment Behaviour, Risk Preference, Investment Decision Making

Introduction:

In today's fast-changing world, managing money wisely has become more important than ever. For this type of money management, the aspects like investment and different sources of investment, knowledge regarding these investment avenues are most prominent for consideration. With so many investment options

available—like fixed deposits, gold, shares, and real estate—people have different views and preferences about where and how to invest their money. This study aims to understand what people think and feels about different investment avenues. It looks at their awareness, the factors that influence their choices, how much risk they are willing to take, and how satisfied they are

with their investments. By learning about investors' attitudes and perceptions, we can get a clearer picture of their behavior and decision-making process. This can also help financial planners, companies, and policymakers offer better investment options and services to meet people's needs.

Objectives:

1. To study the different investment avenues.
2. To assess the level of awareness and knowledge of investors regarding various investment avenues.
3. To find out the factors influencing investment decisions of investors.

Research Methodology:

1. Data Required:

a) Primary Data: Factors that motivate perception of customers regarding different investment options.

b) Secondary Data: - Theoretical concepts about investors attitude and perception towards different investment options with respect to Satara city. This data is sufficient for the purpose of the project work.

2. Source of data: The data required above is to be collected using following sources.

a) Primary data source: Primary data was collected with the help of well-structured questionnaire from the respondents.

b) Secondary data source: The secondary data is obtained from books, magazines, websites and journals.

3. Sample Size: Researcher has taken 122 Samples From Satara City for conducting this research.

4. Sample Technique: The researcher has adopted convenient sampling method to select the sample.

Data Analysis:

Table No 1: Which investment avenues are you familiar with from the following options?

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Fixed Deposits	40	32.79%
2	Gold/ silver	35	28.69%
3	Stock Market (Shares)	30	24.59%
4	Real Estate	12	9.84%
5	Others	05	4.09%
Total		122	100%

(Source: Primary data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that fixed Deposits (33%) are the most familiar investment avenue among respondents, followed by Gold/Silver (29%) and Stock Market

(25%). Real Estate and Others have lower familiarity at 10% and 4% respectively. This suggests a preference for traditional and safer investment options.

Table No 2: Are you aware of different investment avenues?

Sr No	Particular	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	111	90.98%
2	No	11	9.02%
Total		122	100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that a large majority (91%) of respondents are aware of different investment

avenues. Only 9% reported a lack of awareness. This indicates strong financial awareness among the surveyed group.

Which factors influence your investment decisions?**Table No 3: Safety of Capital**

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Important	23	18.85%
2	Slightly Important	22	18.04%
3	Important	23	18.85%
4	Very Important	54	44.26%
Total			100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that most respondents (44.26%) consider the safety of capital as a very important factor in investment decisions. Only a small

portion (18.85%) rated it as not important or important. This indicates that investors highly prioritize the protection of their capital when making investment choices.

Table No 4: Return on Investment

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Important	11	9.02%
2	Slightly Important	28	22.95%
3	Important	31	25.41%
4	Very Important	52	42.62%
Total			100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that the majority of respondents (42.62%) consider return on investment as very

important. A smaller portion (9.02%) regard it as not important. This indicates that investors place strong emphasis on earning satisfactory returns when making investment decisions.

Table No 5: Liquidity

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Important	8	6.56%
2	Slightly Important	23	18.85%
3	Important	41	33.61%
4	Very Important	50	40.98%
Total		122	100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that most respondents (40.98%) consider liquidity as very important in investment

decisions. About one-third (33.61%) also view it as important. This shows that investors highly value the ease of converting investments into cash without significant loss.

Table No 6: Tax Benefits

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Important	6	4.92%
2	Slightly Important	31	25.41%
3	Important	37	30.33%
4	Very Important	48	39.34%
Total		122	100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that most respondents (39.34%) consider tax benefits as very important when

making investment decisions. About 30.33% also rate it as important. This suggests that investors significantly value tax advantages as a key factor influencing their investment choices.

Table No 7: Past Experience

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Important	14	11.48%
2	Slightly Important	29	23.77%
3	Important	37	30.33%
4	Very Important	42	34.42%
Total		122	100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that a majority of respondents (34.42%) consider past experience as very important in

their investment decisions. Around 30.33% also view it as important. This indicates that investors rely significantly on their previous experiences when making future investment choices.

Table No 8: Risk Tolerance

Sr No	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
1	Not Important	18	14.75%
2	Slightly Important	27	22.13%
3	Important	31	25.41%
4	Very Important	46	37.71%
Total		122	100%

(Sources: Primary Data)

Interpretation:

From the above table and graph it is interpreted that most respondents (37.71%) consider risk tolerance as very important in their investment decisions. About 25.41% also rate it

as important. This indicates that investors give significant consideration to their ability to handle risk before making investment choices.

Findings:

1. From the table and chart number (4.1) researcher found that most respondents are familiar with Fixed Deposits, followed by Gold/Silver and the Stock Market. This shows that people prefer traditional and safer ways to invest their money.
2. From the table and chart number (4.2) researcher found that most respondents have a moderate level of investment knowledge. Few people have very low knowledge, showing that there's still some room to learn more.

3. From the table and chart number (4.3.1) researcher found that most respondents think that keeping their money safe is very important when investing. Only a few people give less importance to capital safety, showing that investors mostly prefer secure options.
4. From the table and chart number (4.3.2) researcher found that most respondents feel that getting good returns is very important when investing. Only a few people don't consider returns important, showing that profit is a key factor in investment choices.
5. From the table and chart number (4.3.3) researcher found that most respondents think

it's very important to easily turn their investments into cash. This shows that investors prefer options that offer quick and safe access to their money.

6. From the table and chart number (4.3.4) researcher found that most respondents see tax benefits as an important part of their investment decisions. This shows that saving on taxes is a major reason why many people choose certain investments.
7. From the table and chart number (4.3.5) researcher found that most respondents give importance to their past experience when making investment decisions. This shows that investors often depend on what they've learned from previous investments to guide future choices.
8. From the table and chart number (4.3.6) researcher found that most respondents think their ability to handle risk is very important when investing. This shows that investors carefully consider how much risk they can take before making decisions.

Suggestions:

1. Organize financial literacy programs to help investors make informed decisions.
2. Promote awareness of modern investment options to encourage portfolio diversification.
3. Provide risk management training to help investors balance risk and return.
4. Improve digital investment platforms to attract younger, tech-savvy investors.
5. Promote tax-saving schemes to encourage more people to invest.
6. Build investor confidence through transparency and secure investment products

Conclusion:

The study concludes that investors mainly prefer traditional and safe investment options,

with strong emphasis on capital safety, reasonable returns, liquidity, tax benefits, past experience, and risk-bearing capacity. Most respondents have a moderate level of investment knowledge, indicating awareness but also the need for further financial education. The findings highlight a cautious investment approach, where security and profitability are key decision factors. The suggested measures, such as improving financial literacy, promoting modern investment avenues, enhancing digital platforms, and encouraging tax-saving schemes, can help investors make informed, confident, and diversified investment decisions.

References:

1. Kartika, R., & Kumar, S. K. (2017). A study on investors' attitudes toward investment avenues with special reference to Perambalur District. *IJRDO – Journal of Business Management*, 3(6), 127–135.
2. Velmurugan, G., & Selvam, V. (2015). An empirical analysis on perception of investors towards various investment avenues. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(4), 427–435.
3. Ranjith, V. (2016). A study on the investors' perception towards different investment avenues. *GAP Interdisciplinarity*, 1(1), 83–87.
4. Rao, G. C. (n.d.). Investors' perception towards various investment avenues: A study in Vijayawada city of Andhra Pradesh. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 6(1), 19–26.
5. Ta, S. (2010). A study on investors' perception and attitude towards investment avenues. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 5(2), 619–623.
6. Gopal Krishna, U. M., & Suresh, A. (2011). Perception of investors towards risk in various investment avenues. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 2(4), 1401–1411.
7. Gopal Krishna, U. M. (2019). Investors' perception towards investment avenues. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, 8(2), 1401–1411.